

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Climate Farm Demo is a unique pan-European network of Pilot Demo Farmers covering 27 countries all pedo-climatic areas. The aim is to accelerate the adoption of Climate Smart Farming practices and solutions by farmers and all actors of the Climate Smart Agriculture Knowledge & Innovation Systems.

The wider objective is to adapt agricultural production systems to climate change and achieve a carbon-neutral agricultural sector by 2050, thereby meeting the targets of the EU Climate Strategy.

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WELCOME TO THE HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT

CLIMATE FARM DEMO NEWSLETTER #2

SYNERGY DAYS

Synergy Days in Thessaloniki, October 4th-5th, is just around the corner. We're thrilled to announce our participation alongside Luis Mira da Silva and Maria Mendonça, advisors from CONSULAI - the largest advisory company in the agri-food sector in Portugal and a valuable partner on the Climate Farm Demo Project - who are working on building synergies between Projects, Initiatives and Policymakers, at EU and national level.

Why is this significant? Synergy Days unites digital innovators in the European agri-food sector, providing a stage for experts to share knowledge, spark discussions, and pave the way for a greener future. We're excited to showcase our commitment to sustainability and collaborate with industry leaders. Stay tuned for more updates on our social media channels!

LAUNCH OF THE CLIMATE SMART ADVISORS

We are thrilled to announce that our sister project, Climate Smart Advisors, has officially commenced!

The kick-off meeting took place in Brussels, Belgium, from May 30 to June 1, 2023, marking the commencement of a seven-year project involving 27 countries and 72 institutions. The goal of Climate Smart Advisors is to empower 1,500 farm advisors and promote Climate-Smart Farming practices across Europe. Innovative methods, training kits, and various tools will be shared, tested, and assessed, drawing from the FarmDemo knowledge repository.

PEOPLE BEHIND THE PROJECT

FOLLOW US STAY TUNED

To stay updated with all the latest developments, events, insightful content, and objectives, we invite you to follow our project's social media channels.

By following **#ClimateFarmDemo** on social media, subscribing to the newsletter, and tuning in to the YouTube channel, you'll be at the forefront of innovation and inspiration.

Let's embark on this adventure together, for a greener and more sustainable future! Follow us today and be a part of our thrilling story!

The Climate Farm Demo (CFD) project was launched on October 1st 2022 and got off to a flying start! These first months were mainly devoted to preparing the activities of the 1,500 pilot demonstration farms (PDFs): a massive in-house investment has been made to select audit tools, capitalise practical solutions to help farmers to adapt to climate change, or mitigate the impact of their production systems on climate change; and produce the operational guidelines that are essential at every level. This first year has also enabled CFD's team to engage in dialogue and listen to the expectations of our European referents in order to strengthen and streamline interactions; and create the essential synergy within the project. A lot of energy was dedicated by all the project partners to recruit more than 250 advisers, who in turn recruited the 1,500 PDFs. We also developed the basis for major synergies with the "Climate Smart Advisors" project! This enabled the CFD project to get off to a fast and strong start, with confidence and efficiency.

Christine Berger, IDELE
Project Coordinator and WP9 Leader

